

**FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH
INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI**
**THE ROLE OF ADVERBIAL CLAUSES AND CLEFT SENTENCES IN
COMPLEX SENTENCE FORMATION**

Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

Jizzakh branch of the National
University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
The faculty of Psychology, department of Foreign languages
Phylology and foreign languages

Asilova Yulduz Anvar qizi

Student of group 302-21

Annotation: This article provides a detailed exploration of complex sentences with adverbial clauses and cleft sentences, focusing on their structure, purpose, and practical applications. It begins by defining complex sentences and categorizing adverbial clauses into five types: time, place, reason, purpose, and condition. Examples are included to illustrate their use in various contexts. The article then transitions to cleft sentences, explaining their role in emphasizing specific elements of a sentence. Key types of cleft constructions, such as *it*-clefts and *what*-clefts, are discussed with examples. The piece concludes with practical advice, emphasizing the importance of these structures in enhancing writing clarity and variety. This resource is particularly useful for students, writers, and anyone looking to improve their grammatical precision and stylistic fluency in English.

Key words: Complex sentences, adverbial clauses, time clauses, place clauses, reason clauses, purpose clauses, condition clauses, cleft sentences, *it*-cleft, *what*-cleft, sentence emphasis, grammar, English writing, sentence structure, advanced grammar, writing skills, subordinating conjunctions, dependent clauses, independent clauses.

Understanding Complex Sentences and Cleft Sentences: A Comprehensive Guide

In English grammar, understanding complex sentence structures is key to developing fluency and sophistication in your writing. Among the most common types of complex sentences are those with **adverbial clauses** of time, place, reason, purpose, and condition. Another important advanced structure is **cleft**

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

sentences, which are used for emphasis. This article explores these grammatical features in depth with examples.

Complex Sentences with Adverbial Clauses

A **complex sentence** is formed by combining an independent clause with one or more dependent (subordinate) clauses. Adverbial clauses are a type of subordinate clause that function as adverbs, providing more information about the main verb in terms of time, place, reason, purpose, or condition.

a) Adverbial Clauses of Time

Adverbial clauses of time describe when the action of the main clause takes place. They are introduced by subordinating conjunctions like **when, while, after, before, since, until, as soon as, or whenever**.

- **Examples:**

- I stayed at home **until the rain stopped**.
- **After she finished her homework**, she went to bed.
- He called me **as soon as he arrived**.

b) Adverbial Clauses of Place

These clauses indicate where the action of the main clause occurs and are introduced by conjunctions such as **where** or **wherever**.

- **Examples:**

- You can sit **wherever you feel comfortable**.
- The treasure was hidden **where no one could find it**.

c) Adverbial Clauses of Reason

Adverbial clauses of reason explain why something happens, often introduced by conjunctions like **because, since, or as**.

- **Examples:**

- He didn't attend the meeting **because he was unwell**.
- **Since it was raining**, we decided to stay indoors.
- I left early **as I had another appointment**.

d) Adverbial Clauses of Purpose

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

These clauses describe the purpose of the main action, often introduced by **so that** or **in order that**.

- **Examples:**

- She spoke slowly **so that everyone could understand her**.
- They practice every day **in order that they can win the tournament**.

e) Adverbial Clauses of Condition

Adverbial clauses of condition express conditions under which the main clause occurs. They are introduced by subordinating conjunctions like **if**, **unless**, **provided that**, or **as long as**.

- **Examples:**

- **If you study hard**, you will pass the exam.
- I won't go **unless you come with me**.
- You can borrow my car **as long as you return it by tonight**.

Cleft Sentences

A **cleft sentence** is a construction that divides a single clause into two parts to emphasize a specific element of the sentence. It often begins with phrases like **It is/was...** or **What...**

Types of Cleft Sentences:

a) *It-Cleft Sentences*

In these sentences, the focus is placed on a particular word or phrase by placing it after **It is/was**.

- **Examples:**

- **It was John who fixed the car**.
- **It is the weekend that I look forward to the most**.

b) *What-Cleft Sentences*

These sentences emphasize a particular idea using the construction **What... is/was....**

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

- **Examples:**
 - **What I need is a good night's sleep.**
 - **What he loves most is cooking Italian food.**

c) Other Cleft Variations

Other types of cleft constructions include **All-clefts** and **Wh-clefts**:

- **All-cleft:** All I want is some peace and quiet.
- **Wh-cleft:** Where I'm happiest is by the beach.

Combining Complex Sentences and Cleft Sentences

For added complexity and style, adverbial clauses can be combined with cleft constructions.

- **Example:**
 - **It was because of the storm that the flight was delayed.**
 - **What I remember most is how beautiful the sunset was.**

Conclusion

Mastering complex sentences with adverbial clauses and cleft sentences can elevate your writing by making it more nuanced and precise. While adverbial clauses enrich the main idea by adding details of time, place, reason, purpose, or condition, cleft sentences allow you to emphasize specific parts of your message. Practice integrating these structures into your writing to communicate effectively and with sophistication. Understanding and using complex sentences with adverbial clauses and cleft sentences is not only about mastering grammar rules but also about enhancing your communication skills. These structures allow you to convey detailed information, highlight important points, and add variety to your writing. By practicing these sentence types, you can make your writing more engaging, persuasive, and precise. Whether you're writing academic essays, creative stories, or professional documents, these tools will help you articulate ideas clearly and effectively. Keep experimenting with these structures to refine your style and captivate your audience!

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

REFERENCES

1. Azar, B. S., & Hagen, S. A. (2016). *Understanding and Using English Grammar* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.
2. Carter, R., & McCarthy, M. (2006). *Cambridge Grammar of English: A Comprehensive Guide*. Cambridge University Press.
3. Celce-Murcia, M., & Larsen-Freeman, D. (1999). *The Grammar Book: An ESL/EFL Teacher's Course* (2nd ed.). Heinle & Heinle.
4. Greenbaum, S., & Quirk, R. (1990). *A Student's Grammar of the English Language*. Longman.
5. Hewings, M. (2013). *Advanced Grammar in Use* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
6. Parrott, M. (2010). *Grammar for English Language Teachers* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
7. Quirk, R., Greenbaum, S., Leech, G., & Svartvik, J. (1985). *A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*. Longman.
8. Teshaboyeva, N., & Mamayoqubova, S. (2020). COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 409-414).
9. Teshaboyeva, N. (2020). LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY, ITS STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE NEW PERSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 415-420).
10. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2019). TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERATURE IN TESOL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. In СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ (pp. 82-84).
11. Хидирова, Д., & Тешабоева, Н. (2022). Pedagogical conditions for the development of the healthy thinking in students. Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari, 1(1), 120-122.
12. Gaybullayeva, N. D. K., & Kizi, T. N. Z. (2022). THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN TEACHING LANGUAGE LEARNERS FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND MAINLY ENGLISH. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(10), 8-10.
13. Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi, Jurayev Muhammadrahim Murod o'g'li, & Mamirova Munisa Rajab qizi. (2021). Language Learning Culturally and the Role of Literature in Teaching Process. *Central Asian*

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 2(3), 1-5. Retrieved from <https://www.cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/84>

14. Teshaboyeva, N. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM IN PRESENT DAY. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 5(5).
15. Teshaboyeva, N. (2023). THE MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 5(5).
16. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2023, November). Adjective word group and its types. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 59-61).
17. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2023, November). Modifications of Consonants in Connected speech. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 7-9).
18. Teshaboyeva, N., & Rayimberdiyev, S. (2023, May). THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH CLASSES. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 149-153).
19. Nafisa, T., & Marina, S. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN TESL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 465-469.
20. Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla kizi, & Akramov Ibrohimjon. (2023). WORD FORMATION. COMPOUNDING. "XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 1(12), 109–113. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itftdm/article/view/3187>
21. Teshaboyeva, N., & Yakubova, N. (2023). CHANGES OF MEANING OF WORDS. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(12), 126-129.
22. Sharifova Dinora Tohir qizi, & Teshaboyeva Nafisa. (2023). " NOUNS AND THEIR GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES". *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 292–297. извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/13128>
23. Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla kizi, & Akramov Ibrohimjon. (2023). WORD FORMATION. COMPOUNDING. "XXI ASRDA

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

- INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 1(12), 109–113. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itfttdm/article/view/3187>
24. Qodirova Aziza Yunusovna, & Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi. (2023). "VERBS AND THEIR GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES". *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 280–283. Извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/13126>
25. Tuxtayeva Aziza Ilhom qizi, & Teshaboyeva Nafisa. (2023). Word Formation: Compounding. "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023", 1(12), 113–115. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/cusr/article/view/3185>
26. Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla, & Iskandarova Sarvinoz Shukurullo qizi. (2023). THE CLASSIFICATION OF SYNONYMS AND THEIR SPECIFIC FEATURES. "XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 1(12), 126–131. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itfttdm/article/view/3191>
27. Тешабоева, Н. (2023). Teaching writing as a major part of productive skills in mixed ability classes. *Информатика и инженерные технологии*, 1(2), 652–656. Извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/computer-engineering/article/view/25759>
28. Teshaboyeva, N., & Yakubova, N. (2023). WORD FORMATION. COMPOUNDING. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(12), 187-192.
29. Teshaboyeva, N. (2023). Compound sentences in the English language. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 2(2), 68-70.
30. Nafisa, T. (2023). THE USA ECONOMY, INDUSTRY, MANUFACTURING AND NATURAL RESOURCES OF GREAT BRITAIN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RECENTLY SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHER'S THEORY*, 1(9), 94-97.
31. Nafisa, T. (2023, December). Secondary ways of word formation. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 109-112).

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

32. Nafisa, T. (2023). VOWELS AND THEIR MODIFICATIONS. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 298-305.
33. Nafisa, T. (2023, December). Secondary ways of word formation. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 109-112).
34. Nafisa, T. (2023). THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF THE USA: PRESCHOOL EDUCATION, SECONDARY AND HIGHER EDUCATION, SCHOOL FORMS. *The Role of Exact Sciences in the Era of Modern Development*, 1(6), 53-57.
35. Qizi, T. N. Z., & Umedovich, M. Y. (2023). AMERICAN-BASED PRONUNCIATION STANDARDS OF ENGLISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 2(15), 563-567.
36. Nafisa, T. (2023, December). Word Formation: Compounding. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 113-115).
37. Nafisa, T. (2023). NOUNS AND THEIR GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 292-297.